

EMPIRICAL STUDY OF THE EVOLUTION OF AGILE-DEVELOPED SOFTWARE SYSTEM IN JORDANIAN'S TELECOM

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ABSTRACT

The focus of agile in software development methods and practices. How to take effective methods in use have received less attention. Especially in a large organization is not a little to take in agile methods to use. This paper discusses the adoption and level of experience of the use of agile practices in three companies in the software development company wide contacts in Jordan. The more practices that relied on large-scale flexibility to measure the progress made by the code work, that the developers efforts to the task of estimating, to the use of coding standards, and the lack of overtime continuous, has a team to develop their own operations, to use the limited documentation, and to have the team in one place facility. The adoption of agile practices of the test, any test of the first unit tests and automated, and low. Some can only appear agile practices without the adoption of a conscious, because developers find them useful. So it seems that an emergency operation aimed at agility may also neglect the important agile practices.

KEYWORDS:

Agile Methodologies, Software Development, Agile method, Jordan Telecom.

1. INTRODUCTION

Approach to software development methods and include both agile and plan-driven. Agile methods, and the emphasis on flexibility, informal cooperation and labor law. Supporters argue that agile processes such operations must be able to respond to change and cope with the pressures driving the ongoing evolution of software better than plan-driven approach. Sustainable development of the code is a clear goal in teams flexibility, and is seen as something necessary restructuring and positive [1]. These allegations need to be tested through studies of software development using agile methods. This requires qualitative and quantitative observations by collecting and studying is difficult. He proposed to develop the software includes both the flexibility and plan-driven methods [2].

Agile methods emphasize flexibility, informal cooperation and labor law. Plan-driven approach to emphasize large-scale planning, and official communications and documents. [2]. Proposed five

dimensions of the critical risks (size, forest, and dynamic, and staff and culture) that organizations should be taken into account when deciding which method to use. While the focus of the Boehm and Turner seems to be the situation before and during the initial development, and surveys indicate that the vast majority of the effort the developer is happening in the maintenance and development [3].

The importance of telecommunications and software development led us to propose a strict processes traditionally used to some extent, usually using frameworks such as process, or SW-CMM. As far as we know, no published studies discuss the use of agile methods in the telecommunications industry. Thus, we believe that this paper some light on the current situation. Basic questions in the research that motivated this study are:

1. Which agile practices were used in these telecom companies?
2. What experiences were reported on those practices?

2. RELATED WORK

This study was made in a large telecom company as part of a research program, whose goal is to increase and transfer practical knowledge of achieving agility in software development. Creating a full-fledged methodology and trying to leverage it in a large organization is not feasible. However, describing a set of process patterns that promote agility is more feasible. A process pattern describes a practice considering topics such as which problem it solves, when it is applicable, how to deploy it etc [4].

Wernick & Hall 2004, argued that pair programming should be beneficial for long-term evolution. considers the different types of stakeholders and concludes that the effects of agile methods may be more positive for some than for others. To our knowledge, the findings presented here forms the first measurement-based study of the evolution of software developed using an agile approach in an industrial setting [5].

McCormick, 2001, Ideas for creating a methodology for a company also supports the process patterns approach: "What's needed is not a single software methodology, but a rich toolkit of process patterns and 'methodology components' (deliverables, techniques, process flows, and so forth) along with guidelines for how to plug them together to customize a methodology for any given company." Of course, the ideal content of an agile toolkit depends on the context, and the limits of agile practices are still unclear. Before the study, we had collected a tentative of agile practices that could be applicable in the company. Most of the practices are described in XP and the rest in other literature [6].

This paper aimed at increasing our understanding of the current level of use of these and potentially some other agile practices in the company. Based on the results of this study we will evaluate and improve the practicality and completeness of our tentative agile practice list.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Use the internal network of the company and personal relations, and we have identified several telecommunications companies from the company in the case of Finland, which was a conscious or unconscious use of flexible software development practices. On the other hand, we could not identify any telecommunications company that was using the full agile methodology such as XP. Of seven candidates identified we selected three companies for communications, A, B, C, and that apparently the most active in the use of agile practices. Selected companies and all communications develop different types of products in different business units, and for different markets.

3.1 Sampling Design

Samples are collected through the selection of a sufficient number of elements of Jordan Telecom. We conducted interviews with the director and developer of telecommunications, communications, B, and C, only a developer of communications and interviews covering all areas of a typical software company at a general level in order to identify other agile practices in addition to those which we have already listed.

We quantified the level of use of agile practices in order to answer the research question better first. It was difficult to estimate because there are several dimensions that should be considered, for example, the number of people who use the telecommunications companies, and the duration of use, and discipline to use, and aspects are used. And answered the research question the second qualitative analysis of the experiences reported.

3.2 Instrumentation

Since the polls are usually evaluative rather than generative, they offer the results of a broad and that can be accompanied to the weight. Researchers decided that the survey focused is the best way to collect data on the use of flexible practices in three companies in the software development company wide contacts in Jordan. Quantitative measure for telecommunications companies to use agile practices is:

- Weight (0): Description of practically no benefit from this practice.
- Weight (1): the use of a minor description, for example, and someone tried to practice for some time.
- Weight (2): Use a mild description, for example uses many of the people for a long time.
- Weight (3): description of the use of large, for example, was almost the rule to be used.

4. OVERVIEW OF THE TELECOM COMPANY

Survey includes three companies in the telecommunications sector in Jordan: The company was one of the companies which is published in a small team working in the largest 40 companies from a person sub that was part of the further development of a very large legacy system [3]. The mentality of developers about the company's first two practices, and because the light of the telecommunications company has grown slowly over time, they have the time to find the natural, the process is minimal. Allowed for the success of the product and a small number of developers

to keep them on the process because she wanted in spite of external pressures to change it to adhere better to a model of the general process. Developed a communications company B at a low level embedded software. Director of Communications decided to practices used in the company based on his past experience. Team tried to improve the current process through the deployment of some aspects of certain XP practices. Table 1 summarizes the characteristics of these companies. The company developed a UNIX-based C application.

Table 1. Telecom company characteristics

	company A	company B	company C
company type	Development of a part of a larger system	Integration and porting of embedded sw	Development of an evolving sw product
People	2 (of 40)	4	1 (of 6)
Distribution	Co-located team	Co-located team	Two teams in two countries
Duration	1 years	7 months	Duration 4 years
Effort	~4 man years	~5 man years	~25 man years
SW Size	50 kLOC	12 kLOC	390 kLOC

5. RESULT

5.1 Adoption of Agile Practices

The use of emerging practices more flexible than planned. Usually, the process of individual practices or the use of non-specific or non-formally documented, but instead of the director of the company and developers to use the practices they considered efficient and natural. Have experimented with XP partly in C Company, but others did not use any agile methodology documented as the basis for the operation of their own. Table 2 summarizes the motivation for the use of agile practices and experiences, both with something new, for example some of the practices XP.

Table 2. Presents the adoption level of agile practices and the following Sections describe the experiences

<i>No</i>	<i>Practice</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>B</i>	<i>C</i>
1	Continuous integration	2	0	2
2	Incremental delivery	1	0	2
3	Measure progress by working code	3	3	2
4	Interactive planning	2	0	1
5	Developers estimate task efforts	3	2	2
6	Visual modeling	2	2	1
7	Use cases	0	0	3
8	Design Patterns	2	0	0
9	Continuously developed architecture	2	1	1
10	Pair programming	0	0	1
11	Collective code ownership	2	1	2
12	Coding standard	3	1	3
13	Refactoring	1	2	2
14	Write tests first	0	0	0
15	Limited documentation	3	2	1
16	Team in one location	0	3	3
17	Frequent team meetings	2	1	1
18	Customer always available	2	2	0
19	Team develops its processes	1	2	3
20	No continuous overtime	3	2	1

0: Practically no use 1: Minor use
 2: Moderate use 3: Considerable use

5.2 Evolution of Agile Practices

Continuous integration: in the company, developers integrate their code after a few days of work. The symbol of the work before the check-in. B in the company, developers and sub-systems implemented for the first time on the unit, followed by the stage of integration. C in the company, and checked the new law for the common repository as far as is reasonable, usually after a few days of development.

A gradual transition: the company and was to launch a cycle for 6 months. Company C had a release cycle of 6 months. BP plans to first release occurs after 10 months of start-up company, but was canceled due company for commercial reasons before the first version. Later in the session, were delivered by the weekly bulletins to the customer.

Figure 1. Adoption level of agile practices (1-5).

Measure the progress made by the code work: in a company, and the current version was delivered weekly to the customer. Users tried to pre-release, and provided valuable information to replace the need for a detailed specification requirement. Committed users thanks to the feedback loop are short. Developers are also rewarding to see the results soon. Were divided internally to company B parameters of the program every 1 to 6 weeks.

Interactive Planning: In the company, and Director of the company constantly discussed with customer specifications. He considered the presence of developers in the meetings of the relevant customer is important to gain a common understanding, and give a sense of appreciation for the developers. Priorities have been identified along with customers at various levels (public administration, and features) on the technical feasibility of the proposals also.

Developers appreciate the efforts of the task: in the company, and made crude estimates of effort by the company in the feasibility study, but the developers refine them later. In the estimates of BP originated from an effort in the technical specifications stage, but the development team re-estimated prior to implementation. In the performance of the company C, and the best experts in the field of assessment of the effort. See Figure 1.

Visual Display: In the Company used the scenario and graphics category. The one reason to avoid the graphs to the lack of a good drawing tool. B in the company, and developers is a picture of the whole system shows the parts, communications and they are the most important part of the architectural documentation. Developers and also drew UML scenario diagrams and process sub-systems. C in the company, including technical documents only a few schemes. See Figure 2.

Use cases: in company B, and use case modeling did not use, because the company was mostly technical, and the low level of development. C in the company has been documented requirements using use cases.

Design patterns: the company began to use design patterns after the first major restructuring of the product. In company B, was not considered because of the design patterns applied to coding on a low level.

Figure 2. Adoption level of agile practices (6-10).

Architecture is constantly evolving: in a company, has been developed in parallel with the structure of new features. Submitted a (b) at a higher level design early on the basis of external standards. Remained largely stable design.

Pair programming: problems in Company C code has been solved in many cases, with a pair, but during the programming tasks pairing was scarce. However, even spread that amount of pairing at the correct knowledge of the system among developers. Figure 2.

Collective ownership of code: the company, and allowed the developers to change the code of others, and even the platform code. B in the company and developers have worked mostly with their own code. Sometimes read as a symbol of others, but the owner make the changes final. C in the company, and was allowed a developer to change any part of the law if necessary, but in fact it was focused on units of their own.

Coding standard: in the company, and followed a general pattern of evidence by the company. B in the company, and covered the windows instructions only unit. C in the company, and followed the pattern of evidence in the naming of variables, and structure of the symbol, and symbol in the organization of files.

Restructuring: the refactoreries rarely so as not to break the list, and a large code base. However, not all developers refactor continuously, causing some parts to decay very badly. Kept the senior people in the best form of code. Company B changed low-level design quite a lot during encoding. Company C of the company, and was always present architectural decay has also been adding new features, and was restructuring exercise all the time. See Figure 3.

Figure 3. Adoption level of agile practices (11-15).

Write the first tests: not one of the companies studied and wrote unit tests before the code is real.

Documents are limited: in the company, technical documentation and documents received from the architecture and some short technical guideline documents. These were not usually kept up to date. And considered it somewhat useful for new people, but vocational training such as hands-on training was the most successful knowledge transfer. No senior developer does not need the documents at all. Not developed even in the two sites do not seem to need more documents.

BP had a short technical document for each subsystem and describe the general structure of the system. The need to design documents low because the size of the program was rather small, and had a modular structure. Put only one person each subsystem, and only the interfaces of interest to others. Commenting on the details and the reasons behind the solutions in the source code. The suspension is important even for the writer because of the new domain. The requirements were collected in a short document. There was only one condition a real user and some technical requirements see Figure 3.

Team in one place: in the company and added that the team work in another country for the company. After several months of vocational training in Jordan, the team members began to work in their home. Teams held frequent conferences, and some meetings and workshops annually. The lead developers of the private rooms and the other worked in the Office of the landscape, and that some developers did not like because of the annoying background noise. The companies B and C, two adjacent rooms.

Frequent meetings of the Group: Company to hold meetings when necessary, usually 15-30 minutes once or twice a week. BP had a weekly status meeting, where everyone said what he had done since the last meeting. Company C, ate lunch together, and the Panel did not consider it necessary to hold formal daily meetings.

Customer is always available: in the company, there was a weekly meeting between the customer and the Director of the company and some developers. There were also many discussions with the client. B in the company, played the role of product manager for clients. His room was in another floor, but he answered questions when asked. C in the company, and played the role of Director of the company customers. It was difficult to identify the client's real and proper to have the involvement of the customer.

Figure 4. Adoption level of agile practices (16-20).

Development team operations: in the company, the planning team practices, experimenting with XP, but the process has been defined outside the team. I love the team and the way they worked, and the lack of clear roles, such as designers, managers and programmers to improve team spirit. B in the company, and create a director of the process and discussed with the team. The developers are more interested in software development, and therefore the proposal, the light did not meet with resistance. C in the company, and create a director of the operation along with the team. See Figure 4.

No additional constant: people working in the company extra time just before the launch of the mission. BP used some extra time to speed up the release of the first. Company C increase in stoppage time at the end of the company, but was not significant.

6. DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

6.1 Adoption Level

The most practices often and thoroughly adopted to measure the progress made by the code work, after the developers appreciate the efforts of the task, using the standard encoding, and not to use overtime continuous, and a team development process of their own, limited documentation, having a team in place one. Some practices, such as interactive planning, and writing tests first, and unit test automation, and customer writes acceptance tests, and used the pair programming almost anywhere. It may be that familiarity with these practices was low among those who were interviewed and some very strange practices and difficult for the adoption of practices that cause not only shows. May be that you must create a systematic process based on some documented agile or a list of best practices in order to be the adoption of these practices. As often is the practice test flexibility as a prerequisite for many other practices which are graceful, and the adoption of these practices is low to indicate that there is a need for more education in this area.

6.2 Success Factors

Helped in the company, and held frequent meetings the details of the design team high initial level specifications. Correct pairing during exercise was very useful and dissemination of knowledge between the system developers. The members of one of the strengths of B Company. Director of the company and developers selected on the basis of their skills and qualities in order to form a good team for this company. The director of the company, both administratively and technically competent design and overall architecture. We identified the following success factors

in companies. C in the company, and stayed with the company architects, refectories architecture continuously and the completion of the survival and development of architecture. He became the first developer director of the company, so management decisions taken quickly by the person who was the best technical knowledge of the program. Remained representative of the client himself, and can be done to build mutual trust.

6-3 New Practices

Been identified the following additional practices. Power of art, for example, a director of technically competent improves agility because this person is able to make decisions quickly. Understand the company's manager of technical detail increases the likelihood they have the courage to cut controls such as administrative documents, and review the company of this process. Continuation of the team, and this means that the key to survival of people within the company, because it improves the efficiency of information is maintained implicitly as happened with the architectural firm in C.

7. CONCLUSIONS

This paper was presented experiments on the use of agile methods in the three companies in the telecommunications sector. The use of emerging practices more flexible than planned. Usually, individual practices were not formally defined or processes. Instead, practiced corporate managers and developers is the use of efficient and natural. Generally were satisfied with both corporate managers and software developers with the current development processes compared to their past experiences with processes heavier, more formal. Can do what they see as important (programs) and see concrete results soon through customer shipments frequently. This may explain the positive tone of the debate when interviewed about their companies.

The level of adoption of agile testing practices, any writing tests first unit tests and automated, which is typically use is an important prerequisite for the agile practices of several other, was low. It is clear that there is a need for more information on these practices among companies. Can be seen as the emergence of agile practices without conscious adoption of a good sign, indicating that agile practices are considered useful by the developers themselves. However, it seems that may be neglected practices of several important, if not the process, its goal is to be agile to create awareness, but instead shows only. Practices of agile feet, for example, patterns of a process that can help in finding the most appropriate and dissemination practices more efficiently.

8. REFERENCES

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